

Research Paper

Formative Evaluation of the Diaspora BRIDGE Initiative in Nigeria: An Exploration of SWOT Analysis for Implementation Strategies

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ABSTRACT: In view of the debilitating effects and growing concerns about the brain drain syndrome in Nigeria, the need to leverage the wealth of experience and resources from the Nigerian Diaspora for educational development, in particular, and national development in general, has become more imperative now than ever. It is this need that obviously informed the Nigerian government's initiative on Bridging Research, Innovation, Development and Global Engagement (BRIDGE). This paper conducts a formative evaluation of the BRIDGE initiative, whilst using the framework of the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis to identify the initiative's latent challenges and evident prospects. The paper makes several informed observations: first, that the intrinsic strengths and opportunities of the initiative can largely be guided and catalyzed with the tenets of citizen diplomacy; secondly, that the use of digital diplomacy is also a plausible strategy for the implementation and sustenance of the initiative; thirdly, that all agencies directly or ultimately linked with the administration of the initiative should necessarily eschew the excessive traditional Nigerian red-tapism, as any undue bureaucracy would be inimical to the doctrines of efficiency and transparency that are imperative in the development cum implementation process of BRIDGE.

Keywords: Formative, Evaluation, BRIDGE Initiative, SWOT Analysis, Implementation, Strategies

I. Introduction

Over the years and in recent times, Nigerians with enviable human resources potential have left in droves for greener pastures in foreign countries. This has resulted not only in the problem of human capital flight, otherwise known as the brain drain syndrome, but also prompted the continuous search for the pathways to either reversing the trend and/or tapping into the inadvertent advantages of the syndrome. The two major ways of tapping into the Diaspora population are through financial and educational remittances, but in Nigeria undue emphasis has been placed on the undeniable gains from Diaspora financial remittance

(Nnabuihe, et al, 2024). To this effect, less attention has been devoted to the quest for educational inputs from the Diaspora. History kindly remembers Dr Fred Medrick, who founded Teachers Without Borders (TWB), with the view to providing Diaspora teachers and educational materials to help reach some educationally disadvantaged communities in Nigeria, although documentary evidence on the impact of this particular initiative by an individual is largely scanty. Similarly, Diaspora organisations such as the Common Ground Initiative, ARISE Nigeria, Nigerians in Diaspora Organization (NIDO), etc have demonstrated some level of dedication in promoting education in Nigeria. Members of NIDO, in particular, are known for channeling their resources, talents and expertise towards the support for intellectual and cultural development in Nigeria. There are other documented efforts on how the Nigerian Diaspora complemented the efforts of government in the areas of school rehabilitation, provision of educational equipment, upgrading of libraries and laboratories etc. However, some of these laudable efforts were known to be stifled by lack of basic facilities on ground, poor enabling environment, dearth of ideological/institutional co-operation, absence of follow-up measures and weak collaborative mechanisms by the Nigerian government (Adu, 2016).

Furthermore, there is no gain saying that hitherto, the Nigerian government has not methodically and sufficiently harnessed much educational resources from the Nigerian Diaspora. The failed experience of Nigeria in thoroughly exploiting the educational opportunities of the Second World Black and African Festival of Arts and Culture (FESTAC) in 1977 is an awful example of government's deficiency in the follow-through measures requisite for the harnessing of those opportunities. Whilst the historic event of FESTAC attracted large number of highly learned Nigerian and African Diaspora, there was "no sustained, systematic and determined effort to convert" the ideals of the festival in concrete educational gains for the country (Uya, 2005, p.175).

The foregoing explains why any opportunity, initiative or programme on how to leverage the educational prospects from the Nigerian Diaspora needs to be subjected to careful evaluation. In doing so, formative evaluation becomes apt because it is a disciplined approach not only directed at ensuring that a programme is well designed and developed, but it also allows for an "independent constructively critical input" into the design, development and implementation process of the programme (Kpolovie, p34). The cardinal aim of this sort of evaluation is to ultimately provide the compass and exploratory pathways that would guide both policy makers and policy catalysts to avoid the problems of missteps and inhibitions, right from the onset of policy design through to the process of development and implementation. Therefore, formative evaluation as a diagnostic process conducted in course of the development of a programme, with the aim to improve its quality outcome, becomes imperative in the case of BRIDGE as programme that is awaiting full development and implementation.

II. The BRIDGE Initiative

Whilst an exact total is elusive, Nigeria has a massive and highly educated Diaspora. As at 2012, it was estimated that over 8 million Nigerians were living and plying their trade abroad, many of whom are professional teachers, organic intellectuals, brain trusts and research experts. These groups of Nigerians, who are known to be massively contributing to the global knowledge industry, are found in the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia and other parts of Asia. This is in addition to the thousands of Nigerian overseas students, who are known for not returning to their home country after training or studies (Nyewusira & Nyewusira, 2021). Remarkably, the current Minister of Education, Dr Maruf Olatunji Aluasa, has not only identified the potential in these crop of Nigerians but has floated a policy scheme to facilitate a linkage between them and their compatriots at the home front through an educational initiative tagged Diaspora BRIDGE. BRIDGE is an acronym for Bridging Research, Innovation, Development and Global Engagement. A product of an unprecedented ministerial cooperation between the Federal Ministry of Education and the Nigerians in Diaspora Commission (NiDCOM), the initiative was, inter alia, expected to ensure that Nigeria and Nigerians do not miss the benefits in the global educational advancements through the exploits of their citizens living abroad. The Minister's push for the initiative also stems from the conviction that countries like Japan and South Korea have successfully leveraged the expertise of citizens trained in the Diaspora to support, strengthen and sustain their local educational systems (Anyagafu, 2025).

At the inauguration of the initiative on July 28, 2025, the Minister noted that for several years, the nation helplessly watched the migration of loads of brilliant Nigerian researchers and teachers, who have turned out to be quite outstanding and phenomenal for breaking new paths in institutional innovation and development at the international stage whilst staying overseas. He, however, remarked that with the platform of BRIDGE, Nigeria was not necessarily expecting that the migrants come back home but that it would be rather gratifying if the platform is used to extract their knowledge and contributions for further enrichment of local higher institutions and research centres in Nigeria, regardless of their distance afar off from home (News Agency of Nigeria, 2025). Despite the policy brief on BRIDGE, there are palpable skepticisms on whether Nigeria can actualize and maximize the vision behind this initiative and/or whether the initiative can even survive the test of time. These pessimisms are predicated on the fact that there have been many other national visions, initiatives and programmes that were never fully implemented or that ended up as wild goose chase (Bolaji, 2026). Besides, making a sound policy pronouncement and exciting people's expectations on an outcome, as the Minister of Education made on BRIDGE, without further insight on the evaluation of the strategies that would effectively catalyze the policy, is not just synonymous with the problem of "enunciating new policy statements or in perfecting change in rhetoric than in implementing or institutionalizing change", it is also a sure indicator to '*why educational policies can fail*' (Psacharopoulos, 1990, p.19). Therefore, for the avoidance of such problem or failure in BRIDGE, there is the need for a formative evaluation of the initiative, using the SWOT analysis as a model for practicable development and plausible implementation strategies.

III. Aim of the SWOT Analysis

The SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) analysis is a valuable and strategic tool for evaluation of corporate or public policies, programmes or initiatives through the examination of internal factors (Strengths, Weaknesses) and external conditions (Opportunities, Threats) in order to insightfully understand the variables that would make a policy practicable or impracticable, sustainable or unsustainable. The use of SWOT analysis in this study, therefore, is mostly expected to aid apposite appraisal and necessary adjustments that could lead to a better design, development and attainment of the cardinal goal of the BRIDGE initiative. Suffice it to say that despite its limitations and criticism in academic circles, the adaptation of SWOT analysis remains valuable for formative, process and outcome evaluations. In essence, SWOT analysis would immensely assist those saddled with the planning and implementation of BRIDGE by providing the hindsight for pragmatic decision-making, identification of pitfalls, and the right strategies necessary for the overall accomplishment of the initiative.

Strengths/Opportunities in BRIDGE

BRIDGE, as an educational cum digital initiative, was designed to shore up the collaboration in education, research and innovation between Diaspora academics and Nigerian higher institutions; mainly with the intent to bolster foreign and local alliances in pursuit of the development of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM). This is hinged on the emphasis that all the components of STEM have become inevitable for the realisation of a vibrant education system, productive work skills and overall national development in Nigeria (Orij, 2021). The focus of BRIDGE on the prospects of STEM depicts the potential strength of an initiative that fosters innovation and facilitates collaboration among the various sub-sectors of STEM in carrying out mutual educational responsibility. BRIDGE is also a strategic programme intended to reconnect, re-align and re-engage the vast and growing Nigerian intellectuals and technocrats around the world, considering that over the years the collaboration between Nigerian home-based intellectuals and their counterparts in the Diaspora has been hampered by some factors which include: distance, distrust, diplomatic disorientation, etc. Thusly, BRIDGE becomes a latent practical mechanism and opportunity to reduce distance, rebuild confidence and refocus Nigerian diplomatic policies. Also inherent in this opportunity is the cultivation of a tighter and nested sense of nationhood/nation-building amongst the Diaspora. BRIDGE presents more than a strategic opportunity and push for collaboration; it equally offers a clear understanding that the magnificent role of the Nigerian Diaspora in boosting the domestic economy through humongous remittances back home is also replicable with education or can be intentionally extended to the education sector. As such, the initiative provides a robust platform where Diaspora expertise, interests and potential are broadened and extensive. This reverses the years of erroneous and prejudiced perception that the Nigerian Diaspora can merely be handy

as agents of cash flows and transfers. Fundamentally, then, BRIDGE provides prospective opportunities for global knowledge integration, from the vantage point of a cross-border alignment for building a vibrant education system in particular, and by extension, the nurturing of a buoyant human capital base for Nigeria.

Weaknesses/Threats

The deducible threats/challenges facing BRIDGE are not divorceable from the broader and extant infrastructural plus governance weaknesses associated with policy initiatives in Nigeria. First, there is no evidence that the government has adequately developed plans for the varied educational infrastructural requirement for the successful take-off and sustenance of the initiative. Virtual collaboration and digital engagement are indispensable for the effectiveness of the initiative, as the participants of BRIDGE, both at home and abroad, require day-to-day hitch-free communication infrastructure. Expectedly, the verifiably insufficient availability of such infrastructure in Nigeria would only constitute a major threat for an essential and unfettered access to the seamless communication that BRIDGE requires.

Since BRIDGE was essentially conceived as a digital hub to boost transfer of learning to Nigeria, even from the very remote parts of the world, it is difficult to imagine that the initiative would easily fly in the very many Nigerian higher educational institutions with low compliance to demands for digital technologies and some visible apathy to digitisation transitions by lots of analogue academic staff in these institutions. Suffice it to also mention that where internet facilities are available around these institutions, Nigerian lecturers still rely heavily on commercial cyber cafes or their personal mobile devices for access and connectivity without any form of subsidy from the government (Onwuagboke, et al, 2014). These challenges, in addition to Nigeria's epic epileptic power supply and puny broadband internet penetration in some higher institutions located in the isolated regions of the nation, all bring to fore the types of grave threats that await the BRIDGE programme.

Red-tapism and patriotic reservations are indicative of an added form of threat to the development and implementation of BRIDGE. In the recent past, Nigerian consulates and diplomatic missions have not been able to present accurate census, information and profiling of many Nigerians living abroad, even as many of these Nigerians fail to report to the missions based on bureaucratic encumbrances and a lack of thoroughness in the operational activities of the consulates. Again, there is the proven unwillingness on the part of Nigerian professionals abroad to provide their identities or credentials due to an increasing menace of social and cyber insecurity in Nigeria. In addition, some of these Nigerian Diaspora, though professionals in their own rights, are illegal aliens or are on self-exile and have chosen to completely disconnect from their home country due to the general disgust against bad governance/institutions at home and other unbearable circumstances that ab initio forced them out of their fatherland. In some countries, the Nigerian government representation of Diaspora is considered redundant, thereby leaving the Diaspora groups in those countries more often than not ill-organized (Keshi, 2012; Uya, 2005; Adu & Osadola, 2019). Whilst most aspects of these diplomatic, bureaucratic and patriotic fissures are not under the control of the Ministry of Education, they become very observable weak links to the development of smooth collaboration that is a necessity for BRIDGE to thrive.

Furthermore, BRIDGE faces some major stealthy structural issues within the context of either a weak or convoluted inter-ministerial partnership or inter-agency coordination. These structural issues often resonate and impede administrative processes in public initiatives in Nigeria (Ejimofor, et al, 2024). In view of the fact that the web of network for collaboration in the BRIDGE go beyond the Ministry of Education and the Diaspora, to include NiDCOM, and by default the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Nigerian Consulates, it is difficult to rule out the negative impact of the characteristic structural bottlenecks that are associated with the coordination, networking and partnership of the Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) that are either directly or discursively connected with the BRIDGE agenda. Similarly, BRIDGE like every other educational initiative requires strategic and parsimonious funding, but overwhelming research evidence indicates that inadequate funding and financial skimming are recurring decimal for most operational costs in nearly all educational initiatives in Nigeria (Uwakwe & Adiele, 2022). Hence, Bolaji (2026) observes that many in the Diaspora will hesitate to participate in the BRIDGE if the programme falls into the familiar trap of inconsistent funding and financial malfeasance that have plagued past initiatives in education.

IV. Implementation Strategies

Stemming from the preceding evaluation and analysis which shows a mix of the predisposing and inhibiting factors in the BRIDGE initiative, it becomes incumbent to explore the conceivable strategies for ameliorating the inhibiting factors (threats and weaknesses). The components of the strategies include:

1. Citizen diplomacy. Since BRIDGE is partly targeted at rebuilding the trust of the Nigerian Diaspora in order to contribute to the educational development of their country, the intentionality of the use of citizen diplomacy comes to the fore. The perception of the productive capacity of the Diaspora is largely determined by how they are trusted and treated as citizens by their home country (Keshi, 2012; Nwogbaga et al, 2017). Citizen diplomacy, which was popularised by Ojo Maduekwe, the Minister of Foreign Affairs in between 2007 and 2010, entails the creation of an environment in which the state accords optimal regard to its citizens outside and inside the country, with the expectation that the citizens become worthy “ambassadors’ to the country and are patriotically committed to the development of the country.

Citizen diplomacy operates on the basis of reciprocity between the home government and their citizens abroad; the government promptly discharges its services to the citizens as a spur and enablement for the citizens to carry out their unalloyed obligations to their fatherland (Saliu, 2010). Again, quick response to the distress calls of any Nigerian Diaspora in the event of their maltreatment, harassment or threat to life is a token of commitment to citizen diplomacy. This goes to imply that the Nigerian intellectual community abroad must be treated with utmost dignity by Nigerian foreign missions and the government at home. Such dignified treatment is an incentive to promoting the spirit of patriotism that would, in turn, encourage the Diaspora community to willfully, altruistically and proudly take up their duties with BRIDGE.

Since it is manifest that BRIDGE is rooted in the spirit of Pan-Nigerianism and mutual relations, the crystallization and implementation of the initiative cannot happen without the national inspiration and improved evidence of the seriousness of government to stick to the diplomatic terms for citizens' protection and support wherever the citizens may be found across the globe. The capacity of the Diaspora to wholeheartedly participate in BRIDGE is thus dependent on the right national motivation and shared sense of patriotic dedication.

2. Digital diplomacy. The actualisation of ‘Global Engagement’, which is a major component of the BRIDGE initiative, is near impossible without the functions of digital interconnectivity. The wave of information revolution has facilitated the expansion of digital diplomacy, otherwise referred to as E-diplomacy, Virtual diplomacy or Cyber diplomacy. Global knowledge dissemination is an integral part of digital diplomacy. Digital technologies in general do not only help to advance a nation’s foreign policy, they bring knowledge across the globe closer to poorer nations like Nigeria. However, the implementation and management of digital knowledge is only possible in poorer nations that have the basic ability to receive and process digital information (Nyewusira, 2019).

Nigeria’s foreign policy has three key opportunities to exploit from digital diplomacy. These areas are: Consular and Diaspora relations, Nation branding and Networking (Nyewusira, 2019). The implication of this is that Nigeria, through its policies on digital/social media, has to intentionally and consistently keep in touch with its large population in the Diaspora for the constant projection, highlighting and update of the emerging educational challenges and aspirations under the BRIDGE agenda. Therefore, it would be required of the Ministry of Education, NiDCOM, Nigerian embassies, etc to engage their digital and social media handles on keeping nationals outside the country abreast with the evolving educational needs, schemes, opportunities and challenges in higher education whilst expecting the feedback and input from these nationals in the development of tertiary education.

Importantly too, whilst the intent of BRIDGE is to leverage the ability of the Nigerian Diaspora to disseminate and transfer knowledge, the onus of receiving and processing the knowledge lies squarely with the capacity of the educational institutions at home. Regardless of the assertions by the Minister of State for Education, Prof Suiwaba Sai’d Ahmad, that the Ministry is very much aware of how rural universities and colleges in Nigeria have alluded to the fact that this initiative

is undeniably a transformative tool for bridging expertise gaps, there is equally the overwhelming imperative on the need for these higher institutions to also be well equipped with the elementary tools that easily promote digital engagement, if indeed the initiative would be practically rooted in the ideals and practices of “Global Engagement” .

3. Efficiency dashboards. Following the earlier observation of red-tapism in Consulates’ relations with the Diaspora on one hand and amongst government agencies on the other hand, a streamlining for the administration of BRIDGE becomes crucial. The prevention of red tape in Diaspora BRIDGE would involve the creation of efficient transactional channels, evasion of administrative opacity and the riddance of bureaucratic impediments between the Ministry of Education, NiDCOM, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Consulates and the Nigerian Diaspora, as key stakeholders in the administration and implementation of BRIDGE. According to Okotoni (2003), other strategies for surmounting red-tapism consist of accountability timeline and decentralization of authorities amongst the collaborative organs of government that are directly or obliquely involved in an administrative process. In essence, all bureaucracies and agencies linked with the administration of the BRIDGE initiative have to be responsive, accountable and sensitive to the smooth administration of the initiative. BRIDGE should not only be said to be “designed for mutual accountability, measurable outcomes, and real-time engagement between stakeholders” (Anyanwu 2025), its broader design, administration and implementation must be seen to be unimpeded by any form of operational rigidity and bureaucratic snag.

V. Conclusion

The Diaspora BRIDGE initiative is indicative of a classical approach on how to inadvertently turn brain drain into brain gain. It is geared at creating a structured and sustainable interaction between local educational institutions and Nigerian intellectuals offshore. Much as there are observable strengths/opportunities in the initiative, there are also deducible inherent weaknesses and extrinsic threats to it; ranging from the lack in the availability of digital tools to the patriotic fissures and red-tape that can encumber the implementation of the initiative. Nevertheless, there are extrapolations that these weaknesses/threats are surmountable with proper stimulation of citizen diplomacy, digital diplomacy and deliberate riddance of bureaucratic hurdles. Equally, there are strong indications that the Ministry of Education alone cannot manage BRIDGE; hence, within the framework of a robust design of the initiative, the government, via its agencies on foreign affairs, has to deliberately expand the initiative beyond the involvement of the Ministry of Education, NiDCOM and the Nigerian Diaspora to include other relevant stakeholders.

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